

COMMUNICATION IN SOCIAL RELATIONS, COMMUNICATION AND
INTERPERSONAL RELATIONSHIP PSYCHOLOGY

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Abstract: this article, information about the role of communication in social relations of young people, the importance of communication in the life of society, forms and stages of communication, communicative, interactive, perceptive aspects of communication and pedagogical character are given. A person communicates with other people as long as there is. Through the word, through gestures, etc. The good development of communication also depends in many ways on the habit of listening and speaking.

Key words: Nobility, possessive, communicative, interactive, professional pedagogical, communicative.

Communication is a leader among the activities of the activities of people, and meets the needs related to the most important need in man and considering it as a person. Communication is a process of entering into relations during various activities from the needs of the people's collaborative activities within various activity. The activities of each person perform in society include the forms of interaction and interaction.

The concept of communication soaks that it includes the following at the same time:

- a) the process of interaction of individuals;
- b) the process of information exchange between individuals;
- c) the process of attitude of one person to another person;
- g) the process of influencing a person to influence others;
- d) access to sympathy to each other;

e) the process of understanding each other;

There are also people among special pedagogical abilities that cannot be distinguished by specific teaching or gross work. After all, they are necessary for both either. This aspect is appropriate, in pedagogical dialogue. The scientist Scientist V.A. Kan-Kalik gave such thoughts studying such a skill. The pedagogical case is more than two hundred structures in its structure. Communication is one of its most complexities, which is done through it, for the impact of the most basic teacher of pedagogical activity is carried out. Another important skill of the teacher is to organize a long and effective influence with students. Usually, this skill is associated with the teacher with communicative skills. Having professional pedagogical dialogue is an important role of the pedagogical person belonging to the Interperentine Communication. Steachment is interested in a pedagogical point of view, but are more interesting, but poorly studied, and the type of technical communication is called a Novershal form of pedagogical communication. This related communicative ability includes: to get into dealing with strangers, prevent contradiction, to get conflicts, and to take the misunderstandings and contradictions in time, and It is the ability to make it possible to express their interests and feelings, allowing another person to conduct their own interests and feelings, the ability to benefit highly from communication.

G.M. Nandreva proposed the following structure of the dialogue:

1. Communication of the soum: ie the process of exchanging information and information between the introductors.
2. Interactive aspect of the word: ie the process of interacting the parties to social behavior.
3. The conspilate side of the collection: "That is, a complex psychological process associated with the perception and understanding of communication.

Concluding conclusions of the social experience, his human appearance, or even defects are individually, and the ability to communicate in the Communications, the man who is separated from the communication is. 'la cannot. This means that all the activities of all activities are associated. Alisher says of the skills of the person who is treating the Navoi, "sweet words are honey for those who hearts." Therefore, the

pedagogue is important to pay close attention to the culture of speech, it is important that its psychological, aesthetic, physical, and moral aspects are standard. Pedagogue with a culture of high feelings clearly understood the mood and knight of students. Not leaving room for rude, obscene words, the student personality will damage the work of the teacher. Understanding the situation of the student, it is necessary to sympathize, help. This process is carried out in communication.

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